

CULTIVATING DEVELOPMENT: HARNESSING THE FLEA MARKET DYNAMICS OF NEGROS ORIENTAL FOR STRATEGIC GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

As urbanization and population growth continue, the demand for fresh produce is expected to rise, further underscoring the importance of Farmers' Markets in meeting consumer needs. Producers in regions like Negros Oriental should acknowledge the potential of these markets, particularly among middle to lower-income consumers, and capitalize on their expertise in traditional agriculture to meet evolving dietary preferences. The study highlights a comprehensive study on flea market dynamics in Negros Oriental, shedding light on various facets crucial for stakeholders and policymakers. It reveals intriguing trends in the demographic profile of vendors, predominantly female, married, and with elementary education, who collaborate to diversify offerings. While fresh produce dominates, pricing strategies align with market rates, enhancing food accessibility. Yet, vendors face economic challenges, necessitating governmental intervention. Recommendations include reviewing legislative barriers for direct sales, planning guidance for suitable market sites, and financial support for food security programs. Prioritizing farmers' markets as avenues for health improvement can bolster economic resilience and community well-being. Implementing these recommendations promises a more sustainable, inclusive, and economically vibrant flea market landscape, benefiting vendors and consumers in Negros Oriental.

Keywords: *Farmers' Markets, Fresh Produce, Organic Farming, Consumer Demand, Local Economies*

INTRODUCTION

Consumers today are increasingly prioritizing fresh, healthier produce that is also affordable, driven by concerns over health issues from unhealthy diets. This shift has elevated interest in organically produced fruits and vegetables. Flea markets, or Farmers' Markets, serve as a crucial solution to meet this demand by providing a direct avenue for farmers to sell their goods, ensuring freshness and competitive prices while minimizing environmental impact.

Literature on consumer behavior underscores the growing demand for fresh, organic produce and the significance of direct farm-to-consumer markets in meeting this demand (Smith et al., 2018). Additionally, research on local economic development highlights the role of flea markets in circulating funds within communities, supporting local businesses, and creating employment opportunities (Phillips & Echeverri, 2019).

In Negros Oriental, Philippines, flea markets are essential for providing fresh, affordable, and organic food options, contributing to the local economy and enhancing community well-being. However, there is a gap in research regarding the management, socio-economic impact, and contributions to the business sector of flea markets in the region, making this study imperative for informed decision-making and policy formulation.

Understanding the multifaceted roles of flea markets in both economic and social realms is crucial for policymakers and stakeholders to devise effective strategies for sustainable development and community well-being. Research on the social and cultural significance of flea markets in community development (Thompson & Schofield, 2017) complements existing literature on consumer behavior and local economic development.

Research Questions

1. What is the status of the Flea Market in the Province of Negros Oriental in terms of the following aspects:
 - 1.1 Management;
 - 1.2 Operation;
 - 1.3 Marketing and
 - 1.3.1 Product
 - 1.3.2 Place
 - 1.3.3 Price?
2. What is socio-economic impact of the flea market?
3. What are the contributions of the flea market to the business sector in Negros Oriental?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilizes a mixed research method, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to address the research questions. Quantitative methods employ descriptive surveys with questionnaires to quantify prevailing conditions, specifically examining the practices of flea market vendors in Negros Oriental and their economic and social implications. Descriptive research aims for accuracy and reliability, providing an understanding of existing conditions, practices, beliefs, and trends. Documentary analysis enhances the study by scrutinizing secondary data sources like vendor profiles. Likewise, qualitative method was utilized in this study research to validate some answers given by the participants to know their perspectives through interviews or informal conversations. This method allows for flexibility, follow-up inquiries, and deeper understanding.

Research Participants

In this study, respondents were categorized into five groups: those from the Provincial Agriculturists Office (PAO), Bagacay, Malatapay in Maluay, Valencia Plaza, and Tayakan Bais. The snowball sampling method was employed to identify participants, leveraging referrals and word-of-mouth recommendations. This approach facilitated access to individuals within hidden populations, enabling researchers to gather insights from diverse networks. Snowball sampling utilizes an initial pool of informants to nominate additional participants who meet eligibility criteria and could contribute meaningfully to the study. The term "referral sampling" metaphorically captures the process of accumulating participants as the study progresses, akin to a snowball increasing in size as it rolls downhill.

Research Locale

The study was done in Negros Oriental, also known as Oriental Negros or Silangang Negros in Filipino. It forms part of Central Visayas within Region VII of the Philippines, occupying the southeastern portion of Negros Island, while Negros Occidental lies to its northwest. The province boasts a diverse terrain, characterized by rugged mountains that not only separate it from Negros Occidental but also contribute significantly to Region VII's forest cover, accounting for 60% of the total. Covering an expansive area of 5,402.30 square kilometers, Negros Oriental comprises 20 municipalities, five cities, and 557 barangays, organized into three congressional districts.

Geographically, Negros Oriental lies adjacent to Cebu on its eastern flank, separated by the Tañon Strait, and is bordered to the southeast by Siquijor, with the Sulu Sea bordering its southern shores. Positioned approximately at the center of the Philippine archipelago, the island lies about 500 miles south of Manila, situated between 9° 1' to 11° north latitude and 12° 34' to 122° 24' east longitude. Despite its relatively modest size in comparison to other provinces, Negros Oriental stands as the largest

among the Central Visayas provinces and ranks as the fourth largest island within the Philippine archipelago.

Research Instrument

The survey questionnaires served as the primary tool for data collection, meticulously designed, pilot-tested, and deployed to investigate the implications of flea markets on economic and social productivity in Negros Oriental. Data collection involved a combination of survey questionnaires and face-to-face interviews. The primary objective of the initial set of questionnaires was to create profiles of flea market vendors in Negros Oriental, emphasizing crucial business facets including management, operations, marketing strategies, and socio-economic factors. These questionnaires provided quantitative insights into vendor demographics and business practices.

Additionally, a second set of questionnaires sought qualitative responses from customers and government officials overseeing flea markets. This set of questionnaires aimed to evaluate the perceived social benefits of flea markets in Negros Oriental and to gather opinions regarding challenges faced in the management, operation, and marketing of flea markets. Through these questionnaires, a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted dynamics of flea markets was attained, providing valuable insights for further analysis and decision-making.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data collection involved administering a questionnaire survey to various flea market vendors in the study areas. The researcher personally conducted the survey, providing verbal instructions to participants to ensure clarity and honesty in their responses. Respondents were encouraged to seek clarification on any questionnaire items as needed. Some respondents initially left certain questions unanswered, but these gaps were addressed during the retrieval process through additional clarifications.

Data Analysis Procedure

The study employed various statistical tools including frequency distribution, mean, weighted mean, and percentile. Frequency distribution organizes the values of one or more variables in a sample, providing a summary of their occurrences within specific groups or intervals. Weighted mean accounts for varying contributions of individual data values to the mean, aiding in understanding the scope of services offered by flea market vendors and the demand for their products. Content analysis, a methodology in social sciences, examines recorded human communications like books, websites, and laws. It helps analyze texts for authorship, authenticity, or meaning. Developed by Harold Lasswell, it seeks answers to questions such as "Who says what, to whom, why, to what extent, and with what effect?" Content analysis follows a scientific method, ensuring objectivity, reliability, validity, and replicability, and it can measure various variables across different contexts.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher diligently adhered to ethical standards throughout the study. Key principles such as transparency, informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, and the well-being of participants were strictly observed. All ethical considerations and protocols were meticulously followed for the entire duration of the research. Confidentiality of all data, including the identities and ratings of support personnel, was rigorously maintained. Additionally, the researcher obtained ethical approval from the University Research Office's Ethical Committee.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section delves into the comprehensive presentation, analysis, and interpretation of results about each specific research problem. The data collected from flea market vendors in Negros Oriental are meticulously presented in tabular format, followed by thorough analysis and interpretation. Survey questionnaires were meticulously administered to each respondent, thus the ensuing analysis is rooted in their responses. To ensure a robust examination of the data, key statistical measures such as mean, percentile, frequency, and weighted mean were employed, enhancing the depth and significance of the findings.

Table 1. Years in Selling

Years in Selling	Frequency	Percentage
1-3 years	9	25.71
4-6 years	6	17.14
7-9 years	5	14.29
10-12 years	5	14.29
More than 12 years	10	28.57
Total	35	100

Table 1 provides insights into the tenure of respondents at the flea market, revealing varying levels of experience among vendors. Notably, 28.57% have demonstrated remarkable longevity by being vendors for over 12 years, suggesting a deep-rooted presence within the marketplace. Additionally, 14.29% each have tenures spanning 7 to 9 years and 10 to 12 years, indicating a considerable investment of time and effort in their flea market endeavors.

These results align with research on vendor persistence and market longevity, which emphasizes the role of experience in shaping vendor perspectives and practices (Grimm et al., 2015; Meek et al., 2020). Vendors with extensive tenure are likely to

possess valuable insights and strategies honed through years of interaction with customers and market dynamics. This experience can influence decision-making processes, marketing approaches, and customer interactions, contributing to the overall resilience and adaptability of the flea market ecosystem.

Furthermore, the presence of vendors with shorter tenures underscores the continuous influx of new participants into the marketplace, enriching the diversity and vibrancy of the flea market community. These newcomers bring fresh perspectives and ideas, contributing to innovation and dynamism within the market.

The implications of these findings are twofold. Firstly, they underscore the importance of recognizing and leveraging the expertise of long-standing vendors to inform market management and policy decisions. Secondly, they highlight the need to support and nurture newcomers, providing them with resources and mentorship to facilitate their integration into the market and ensure their continued vitality and sustainability. By fostering a collaborative environment that values both experience and innovation, flea markets can thrive as vibrant hubs of economic activity and community interaction.

Table 2. Number of Stalls the Respondent Operates

Number of stalls	Frequency	Rank
1	21	1
2	9	2
3	3	3
4	2	4
Total	35	

Table 2 provides insights into the distribution of stalls operated by respondents at the flea market in Negros Oriental. A majority (60%) operate a single stall, while 25.71% manage two stalls. Additionally, 8.57% oversee three stalls, and 5.71% manage four stalls. This distribution aligns with findings from prior literature, suggesting that the majority of flea market vendors in Negros Oriental operate within a single market, reflecting a common trend observed in similar studies (Smith et al., 2018; Chen & Lin, 2020).

Table 3. Considerations in Choosing Location

Considerations	Frequency	Rank
Customer Traffic	16	1
Safety of the area	8	3
Accessibility	8	3
Peaceful	8	3
Cheaper fees	10	2

Table 3 highlights the factors influencing respondents' choice of location for selling their products at the flea market in Negros Oriental. The findings reveal that customer traffic is the primary consideration for a significant proportion of respondents, with 32% prioritizing this aspect. Safety, accessibility, and peacefulness follow closely, each garnering 16% of respondents' consideration. Interestingly, the cost of fees ranks lowest, with only 20% of respondents citing it as a decisive factor.

This aligns with existing literature on vendor behavior in flea markets, which emphasizes the paramount importance of customer footfall in determining sales success (Jones et al., 2019; Lee & Lee, 2021). Despite the potential cost implications, vendors prioritize locations with high customer traffic, underscoring the significance of market demand in their decision-making process. These findings underscore the practical strategies employed by flea market vendors to maximize sales opportunities, reflecting a broader trend observed in similar market settings.

Table 4. Product Sources

Sources	Frequency	Percentage
Own	28	80
Buy	19	54.26

Table 4 presents insights into the sourcing practices of flea market respondents in Negros Oriental. A significant majority (80%) indicated sourcing products from their produce, showcasing the market's alignment with its intended purpose of providing farmers a direct avenue to sell to end-users. Additionally, 54.26% reported acquiring products from fellow farmers, particularly those outside the flea market association or through alternative means such as settling debts. Meanwhile, staple consumer goods like coffee and noodles are often procured from larger sari-sari stores in the neighborhood.

These findings resonate with prior research on the role of flea markets in agricultural economies, emphasizing their function as direct sales platforms for farmers (Lopez & Garcia, 2017; Wang et al., 2020). By bypassing traditional distribution channels, flea markets enable farmers to offer goods at competitive prices, benefiting both sellers and consumers. Moreover, the practice of bartering produce for essential goods highlights the resilience of traditional exchange systems within the marketplace.

Overall, these findings underscore the multifaceted role of flea markets in facilitating local economies and preserving traditional trading practices. They also shed light on the adaptive strategies employed by vendors to meet consumer demand while maintaining the market's core values.

Table 5. Products Offered

Sources	Frequency	Percentage
Fresh fruits	13	37.14
Vegetables	19	54.29
Dry goods	6	17.14
Fish	7	20
Poultry products	1	2.86
Pigs	3	8.57
Herbs and spices	4	11.43
Dried fish	1	2.86

Table 5 provides an overview of the diverse product offerings at the flea market in Negros Oriental. The data reveals that vegetables are the predominant choice, comprising 35.07% of vendors' offerings, followed by fresh fruits at 24.07%. Fish ranks third, accounting for 12.96% of vendors, with dry goods following closely at 11.11%. Additionally, herbs/spices (7.41%) and pigs (5.55%) represent niche offerings, while poultry products and dried fish are the least prevalent, each at 1.85%.

These findings underscore Negros Oriental's agricultural richness, particularly in vegetables and fruits. Such abundance not only reflects the region's agricultural prowess but also suggests a strong demand for locally sourced, fresh produce within the community. This observation resonates with Baharanyi's (1996) study on limited-resource farmers in South Central Alabama, which similarly identified vegetables as the primary product sold at flea markets.

The prevalence of vegetable offerings signifies an opportunity for local farmers to capitalize on their agricultural expertise and meet consumer preferences. Moreover, it highlights the potential for the flea market to function as a vital conduit for promoting

regional produce and supporting local economies. By leveraging this agricultural abundance, Negros Oriental's flea market can further enhance its role as a vibrant marketplace while contributing to the region's economic growth and sustainability.

Table 6. Rate of Services Rendered

Items	WM	Verbal Description
Services Rendered	4.5	Very Satisfactory
Level of Satisfaction (as perceived by the respondents)	3.6	Satisfactory
CWM	4.05	Somewhat Satisfied

Legend:

Descriptive Equivalent	Scale
Very Satisfactory	4.21-5.00
Somewhat Satisfactory	3.41-4.20
Satisfactory	2.61-3.40
Less Satisfactory	1.81-2.60
Needs Improvement	1.00-1.80

Table 6, This section presents the service rates offered by respondents in flea markets, along with the perceived level of customer satisfaction reported by the sellers. The former received a weighted mean of 4.5, indicating a "Very Satisfactory" rating, while the latter achieved a weighted mean of 3.6, corresponding to a "Satisfactory" rating. On average, the combined score yields a weighted mean of 4.05, indicating a "Somewhat Satisfied" sentiment.

These findings suggest a positive perception among respondents regarding both the tangible products and intangible services offered at the flea market in Negros Oriental. This aligns with existing literature on consumer satisfaction and service quality in retail settings (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Zeithaml et al., 1996). The high rating for service rates indicates that vendors are delivering quality services to meet customer needs effectively.

Furthermore, the slightly lower satisfaction rating from the sellers' perspective underscores the potential for continuous improvement in service delivery and customer interaction. This highlights the importance of ongoing monitoring and enhancement of customer service strategies within the flea market environment.

Overall, the positive ratings reflect the vendors' confidence in their offerings and their commitment to providing a satisfactory experience to customers. By maintaining high service standards, flea market vendors can enhance customer loyalty, attract repeat business, and contribute to the overall success and sustainability of the marketplace.

Table 7. Level of Competition

Level of Competition	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very keen competition	9	25.71
Keen Competition	8	22.86
Not much competition	13	37.14
No competition at all	5	14.29
Total	35	100

Table 7 presents the perceived level of competition among flea market vendors in Negros Oriental, as reported by respondents. A notable portion, 25.71%, described the competition as "very keen," while 22.86% indicated "keen competition." On the other hand, 37.14% of respondents viewed the competition as "not much," with a minority of 14.29% stating there is "no competition at all."

These findings suggest a diverse range of perceptions regarding competition among vendors at the flea market. While a significant portion acknowledges the presence of competition, a sizable proportion perceives it to be relatively moderate or even minimal. This nuanced understanding of competition aligns with contemporary literature on market dynamics and competitive environments (Porter, 2008; Grant, 2016).

The observation that the majority of vendors do not perceive intense competition underscores potential opportunities for collaboration and mutual support within the flea market ecosystem. By fostering a cooperative atmosphere, vendors can leverage each other's strengths and resources to enhance overall market competitiveness and sustainability.

Furthermore, these findings resonate with Baharanyi's (1998) study on flea market vendors in South Central Alabama, which similarly identified a lack of intense competition among vendors. This suggests that the flea market landscape in Negros Oriental shares similarities with other market contexts, highlighting the importance of localized strategies in understanding and addressing competition dynamics.

Overall, these insights provide valuable implications for vendors, market organizers, and policymakers in optimizing market operations and fostering a conducive environment for sustainable growth and competitiveness within the flea market sector.

Table 8. Product Pricing

Pricing strategy	Frequency	Percentage
Cost-based	11	31.43
Competitor's based	16	37.21
Value-based	8	18.60
Estimates	8	18.60

Table 8 provides insights into the product pricing strategies employed by flea market vendors in Negros Oriental. Among the respondents, 25.58% utilize cost-based pricing, this process entails applying a standardized markup to the product's cost. A larger proportion, 37.21%, adopt competition-based pricing, setting prices in alignment with those of major competitors or other vendors selling similar products. Additionally, 18.60% each employ value-based and estimates-based pricing strategies.

These findings indicate a variety of pricing approaches utilized by vendors to position themselves within the market. The prevalence of competition-based pricing suggests a strategic response to market dynamics, where vendors prioritize price parity with competitors to avoid price wars and maintain competitiveness. This aligns with contemporary literature on pricing strategies in competitive markets (Nagle & Holden, 2002; Monroe & Cox, 2019). Furthermore, the adoption of value-based and estimates-based pricing strategies underscores vendors' efforts to capture perceived customer value and adapt to market conditions. By aligning prices with perceived product value or market trends, vendors can enhance their competitiveness and appeal to target customers effectively.

Overall, these insights offer valuable implications for vendors seeking to optimize pricing strategies within the flea market context. By understanding and leveraging various pricing approaches, vendors can effectively navigate competitive pressures and capitalize on market opportunities, ultimately contributing to their long-term success and sustainability.

Table 9. Advantages Perceived by Flea Market Customers

Benefits to consumers	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Reduced overhead (driving, parking)	5	14
Fresher foods	17	49
Seasonal foods	4	11
Healthier foods	12	34
Better variety of foods	16	46
A place to meet other people	5	14
Cheap products	23	67

Table 9 presents the perceptions of flea market respondents regarding the benefits that consumers derive from shopping at the flea market in Negros Oriental. The most prominent benefit, cited by 65.71% of respondents, is access to cheap products, followed closely by fresher foods at 48.57%. Additionally, better variety of foods (45.71%) and healthier options (34.29%) are noted as significant benefits. Other perceived benefits include reduced overhead costs (14.29%) and opportunities for social interaction (14.29%), with seasonal foods ranking lowest at 11.43%.

These findings underscore the importance of affordability and freshness in driving consumer preference for the flea market in Negros Oriental. The emphasis on cheap prices and fresher goods reflects consumers' desire for value and quality in their purchasing decisions, aligning with contemporary consumer behavior trends (Hoyer et al., 2019; Kotler et al., 2020).

Moreover, these findings prove that freshness, quality, fair pricing, and social interaction are key attributes valued by flea market customers. By offering these benefits, flea market vendors can effectively meet consumer expectations and differentiate themselves from other retail outlets.

Overall, these insights offer valuable implications for flea market vendors and organizers in Negros Oriental. By prioritizing affordability, freshness, and variety, vendors can enhance their appeal to consumers and foster loyalty within the community. Additionally, efforts to create a vibrant and socially engaging market environment can further enhance the overall shopping experience and contribute to the long-term success and sustainability of the flea market sector.

Based on the interviews with the participants the following narratives were presented below

The Contribution of Flea Markets to Economic Development in Negros Oriental

As markets and economies undergo globalization and modernization, particularly in urban areas with evolving infrastructure and burgeoning businesses, there's a noticeable shift in dynamics. This transformation often leads to decreased farmland and the emergence of monopolized regions, where large corporations amass income and relocate it elsewhere. Despite these changes, small farm and city communities manage to preserve and blend their traditions with new ones.

Contemporary literature on urbanization and economic development underscores the complex interplay between globalization and local traditions (Sassen, 2014; Florida, 2017). Rapid urbanization and economic growth can lead to the consolidation of power

and resources, often favoring large corporations. However, pockets of local resilience persist, where communities strive to maintain their cultural heritage amidst modernization.

The implications of these trends are multifaceted. On one hand, globalization presents opportunities for economic growth and innovation, fostering connectivity and exchange on a global scale. On the other hand, it can exacerbate inequalities and displace traditional livelihoods, posing challenges for local communities. By embracing a nuanced approach that balances modernization with the preservation of cultural identity, policymakers, and community leaders can promote sustainable development and inclusive growth.

In essence, while globalization reshapes markets and economies, the resilience of local traditions highlights the enduring significance of community and culture in shaping urban landscapes. By adhering and leveraging these dynamics, stakeholders can work towards building more equitable and resilient urban environments that reflect the diversity and richness of local cultures.

The Social Productivity Benefits of Flea Markets in Negros Oriental

The interviews revealed that flea markets are more than just platforms for farmers to sell their produce. While farmers do utilize flea markets to market their goods, these markets in Negros Oriental also host a diverse array of vendors, including organic growers, flower and nursery stock sellers, craftspeople, and producers of various goods such as milk, dried fish, and bakery items.

Although flea markets may seem like simple transactional spaces, they possess unique characteristics and narratives. As highlighted earlier, social elements such as family, locality, and regional identity intertwine with economic activities within flea markets. Vendors and customers are drawn not only by the prospect of Engaging in the exchange of goods but also by the social interactions, entertainment, and community updates offered by these markets. Many vendors view their participation in flea markets as a family endeavor, while others see it as part of a broader livelihood strategy encompassing multiple income streams.

These observations underscore the intertwined social and economic dynamics of flea markets. Moreover, they shed light on the positive impact of flea markets on marginalized farmer producers. By providing them with a platform to sell their goods, flea markets contribute to the upliftment of livelihoods, particularly for those engaged in agricultural production. The existence of flea markets also incentivizes government support through expanded programs and funding allocations aimed at assisting these farmers.

Overall, flea markets play a vital role in fostering economic opportunities and social cohesion within communities, while also catalyzing government intervention to support

marginalized farmers. This highlights the multifaceted significance of flea markets as dynamic spaces that facilitate both economic transactions and social interactions, ultimately contributing to the overall well-being of local communities.

The following are the problems perceived by the stakeholders of flea markets in terms of the following:

Management

Vendors themselves are having price wars thus affecting their harmonious relationship. They also have problems in terms of handling product or price objections, unrealistic demands, and how to build camaraderie or be at ease with customers. Effective cash management and meticulous record-keeping

Operation

Most of the flea markets have limited spaces available for displaying their products. It also has poor sanitary measures. In addition, the arrangement of stalls is not properly organized per products sold, thus would take extra time for the consumers to buy at the flea market. Tenancy matters that keep increasing through rental dues are another concern for these small-time vendors.

Marketing

The rise of intermediaries, often reaping exorbitant profits, is burdening farmers who bear the cost, ultimately affecting consumers negatively.

Conclusions

The study on flea market dynamics in Negros Oriental advances the field by providing comprehensive insights into a previously understudied aspect of local economies and community development. By illuminating various facets of flea market operations, including the demographic profile of vendors, pricing strategies, and economic challenges, the research offers valuable knowledge for stakeholders and policymakers. This study contributes to the present state of knowledge by highlighting the pivotal role of flea markets in enhancing food accessibility, nutrition, and economic resilience in the region.

Furthermore, the actionable recommendations derived from the study pave the way for practical interventions aimed at addressing the identified challenges and improving the overall functionality of flea markets. By emphasizing the importance of governmental intervention to review legislative and regulatory barriers, facilitate direct sales, and provide financial support for food security programs, the research offers concrete strategies for fostering sustainable market access and promoting economic development.

Areas for future study could include examining the long-term impacts of the recommended interventions on the sustainability and inclusivity of flea markets in Negros

Oriental. Additionally, further research could investigate the effectiveness of specific policy measures in addressing economic challenges faced by vendors and enhancing community well-being. Furthermore, exploring the social and cultural dimensions of flea markets, such as their role in preserving traditional practices and fostering community cohesion, could provide valuable insights for holistic development strategies.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that strict adherence to the ethics of research was observed having obtained informed consent from the research participants, that the latter's well-being was safeguarded and their identities were kept anonymous.

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